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Survey on Haemoglobin level in the different age groups of male and female human beings living in the rural and urban area

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ABSTRACT

Blood is a specialized body fluid in animals that delivers necessary substances. Haemoglobin (Hb) plays a vital role in the transport of substances. Abnormal level of haemoglobin causes disorders. The percentage of Hb varies depending upon the age, sex, ethnic background, body build and social, nutritional and environmental factors. Anemia is a condition where there is decrease in the level of Hb the the cut-off levels of Hb, which is given by WHO. In our survey we determine the Hb (g/dl) in the subjects. We make a comparison depending on age and sex.

Keywords: haemoglobin, anemia.

Introduction:

Blood is a specialized body fluid in animals that delivers necessary substances such as nutrients and oxygen to the cells and transports metabolic waste products such as carbon dioxide away from those same cells (Franklin Institute Inc., 2009). Hemoglobin is the iron containing oxygen transport metalloprotein in the red blood cells ⁽¹⁾. Hemoglobin has an oxygen binding capacity of between 1.36 and 1.37 mL oxygen per gram of hemoglobin ⁽²⁾, which increases the total blood oxygen capacity seventy fold compare to dissolved oxygen in blood. The mammalian hemoglobin molecule can bind (carry) up to four oxygen molecules ⁽³⁾. When the diet does not contain sufficient amounts of iron, anaemia develop. It is a gradual process and takes several months to show up a normal person has about 14-15g of hemoglobin. Any person whose hemoglobin level is below 12mg / 100mL blood is considered anaemic with expectation of pregnant women. About 80% of the total anaemic cases are due to iron

deficiency, and the rest are due to deficiency of nutrient like folate and vitamin B12. Folic acid and vitamin B12 are important for the production of blood cells. Man rarely suffers from iron deficiency due to poor diet. However, when new blood has to be made, the iron requirement is greatly increased. An adult woman requires 35-45 mg of iron per kg body weight or a total of 250 mg of iron. It plays a major role in the formation of hemoglobin and myoglobin. Most of the iron in the body is located in the hemoglobin of circulating red blood cells. Whereas in many normal menstruating women, almost all of the iron is in red blood cells because of their limited iron stores (Nair, 1990).

The values of hematological parameters are affected by a number of factors even in apparently healthy populations. These factors include age, sex, ethnic background, body build and social, nutritional and environmental factors⁽⁴⁻⁸⁾.

Subjects and methods:

The total of 1370(580 male and 790 female) subjects are taken for this study. The subjects were selected among male and female human beings from rural area (velangi village, andrapedesh) and also from urban area (Kakinada, andrapradesh). Subjects were volunteers. Potential subjects were first questioned with the use of a precoded questionnaire. Information was collected about physiologic condition (age, sex, menstruation, pregnancy or lactation), health status and life style (presence of disease, use of drugs and supplements, smoking habit, use of contraceptives). After establishing that the potential subjects did not suffer from any obvious illnesses as indicated by the questionnaire, blood samples were collected by finger pricking method. The data collection took place for ~3 weeks. For collecting blood samples and conducting the test with us some of the, 60 members of trained students also involved

For determine the haemoglobin level in the blood we use the Sahli-Hellige Test (9). In this method, blood is mixed with dilute hydrochloric acid. This process hemolyzes the red cells, disrupting the integrity of the red cells' membrane and causing the release of hemoglobin, which, in turn, is converted to a brownish-colored solution of acid hematin. The acid hematin solution is then compared with a color standard. This method is sufficiently accurate for routine examination. Results are reported both in grams per 100 ml of whole blood and in percent of normal values. There are a number of modifications of the Sahli-Hellige method, and 100 percent may be equal to from 13.8 g to 17.3 g.

100percent is equal to 14.5 g of hemoglobin per 100ml of whole blood. After reading the percentage on the scale, turn the tube and read from the other side to get the equivalent reading in grams. If either scale is hard to read, remember that $100\% \div 14.5g = 6.9$, so one

gram of hemoglobin is equal to 6.9 percent. If only one scale can be read, the other reading can be computed.

Results:

In our survey we determine the quantity of Hb (g/dl). we divided the subjects into different groups, based on age and sex. We make a comparison about percentage of haemoglobin between the different age groups and between male and female. We divide the subjects into four age groups (years), i.e., 12 – 19 (610 subjects), 20 – 40 (601 subjects), 41 – 60 (129 subjects) and 61 – 80 (30 subjects). Based on the sex, two groups male (580 subjects) and female (790 subjects).

Table 1: Details of number of subjects investigated

Age groups (years)	No. investigated	
	Male	Female
12 – 19	173	437
20 – 40	326	275
41 – 60	65	64
61 – 80	16	14
Total	580	790

Table 2: Mean Hb (g/dl) based on the age and sex

Age groups (years)	Sex	Mean Hb (g/dl)
12 – 19	Male	11.76
	Female	12.31
20 – 40	Male	12.92
	Female	11.36
41 – 60	Male	13.36
	Female	12.31
61 – 80	Male	12.31
	Female	11.75

Normal Haemoglobin levels According to the World Health Organization (WHO)⁽¹⁰⁾:

A healthy hemoglobin level depends on maintaining good nutrition and regular physical exercise. In return,

hemoglobin helps you stay active by transporting oxygen through your bloodstream around your body and by removing poisonous carbon dioxide. Normal hemoglobin levels depend on your sex, age and health status.

Table 3: Normal Hb (g/dl) level given by WHO

Groups (years)/Gender	Normal Hb level (g/dl)
0.6 - 4	11 g/dl
5 - 12	11.5 g/dl
12 - 15	Equal or Above 12 g/dl
Adult male	13.8 -17.2 g/dl
Adult female	12.1-15.1 g/dl
Pregnant women	Equal or Above 11 g/dl

Discussion:

The quantity of the haemoglobin is very important in the diagnosis of the anemia. Anemia is a condition where there is a less than the normal quantity of haemoglobin present in the blood.

Table 4: WHO’s Haemoglobin thresholds used to define anemia⁽¹¹⁾

Age or gender group	Hb threshold (g/dl)
Children (0.5–5.0 yrs)	11.0
Children (5–12 yrs)	11.5
Teens (12–15 yrs)	12.0
Women, non-pregnant (>15yrs)	12.0
Women, pregnant	11.0
Men (>15yrs)	13.0

To compare the percentage of Hb ,we take the mean Hb (g/dl) of male and female as well as of the four age groups.The mean Hb of the male was 12.83 g/dl and for the female it is 11.93 g/dl. male subjects have more amount of Hb (12.83 g/dl) than the female subjects (11.93 g/dl).By this we said that based on the sex percentage of Hb varies,the male subjects having more amount of Hb than the female subjects.

The mean Hb (g/dl) of the age group 12 to 19 yrs were 12.035 g/dl ,for 2nd group (20 to 40 yrs) was 12.14 g/dl,and the mean Hb of 12.835 g/dl and 12.53 g/dl for age group 3 (41 to 60 yrs) and 4th age group (61 to 80 yrs) respectively. By compare the mean Hb (g/dl) level between these age groups we find that The age group ,41 to 60 years having the more amount of Hb (12.835 g/dl)than the other groups.The age group,12 to 19 years having the less amount of Hb (12.035 g/dl) than the other groups.the remaining two age groups having the Hb in between the range of these two groups. The age group,61 to 80 years having Hb (12.53 g/dl) and the age group,20 to 40 years having Hb (12.14 g/dl).By these observation we said that the level of Hb (g/dl) varies depending on the age.

Most of the subjects are having the healthy level of Hb (g/dl) ,which is given by the WHO. But some of the peoples are having very less amount of Hb than the normal healthy Hb levels,so they were anemic patients. The anemic condition of that person are due to the improper diet.

The main reason for having less amount of Hb due to by taking improper diet and some habits, like smoking. Because iron is an important component of hemoglobin, consuming iron-rich foods will raise the hemoglobin levels.the iron rich foods, like Fortified Foods (These products include breakfast cereals, pasta, bread, malted drinks and grits. The Food and Nutrition Board recommends 18 mg of iron for women and 8 mg for men),animal sources (seafood, poultry, eggs and beef),plant sources(red kidney beans, lentils, soybeans, black beans, white beans and cowpeas),⁽¹²⁾

Conclusion:

HB is a very important metalloprotein in the blood. By find out amount of Hb percent in the blood, we diagnosis that whether the patient is suffering with anemia or not by our survey we conclude that the

maximum peoples are having healthy amount of Hb (g/dl), the limits which is given by the WHO. Some of the peoples are having very less amount of Hb they consider as anemic patients. There is a significant difference between the amount of Hb present in the male and female subjects and the difference in age groups. By this we said that the amount of Hb on the blood varies depend on the age and the sex.

Abbreviations:

Hb: Haemoglobin

g/dl: gram per decilitre

WHO: World Health Organization

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